

Assessment of Construction Hauling Process Accidents and Causes within Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the construction hauling process accident within Tertiary Institution in Rivers State. The specific objectives were to identify the types of hauling process accidents, their causes and challenges in various construction sites within selected Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study. The population for this study comprised male and female within the age of 18 to 60 years above that are working at the various construction sites in the selected four Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Using a simple random sampling technique, a total of 400 copies of questionnaire were administered out of which 385 were retrieved and used for analysis. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used for the analysis. Descriptive statistics involved the use of frequencies and percentages to express the responses from the questionnaire, while the hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation analysis to show the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Findings revealed that 66.2% indicated that manual handling caused accidents at construction sites in the study area. While 66.5% specifically indicated that electric shock at the construction sites is one of the main causes of accident in constructions sites, 42.1% agreed that defective equipment was the another important causes of accident at constructions sites. Thus, the study recommends that risk and safety experts should be contacted to assist in implementing some of the mitigation and personal protective equipment policy as measures to curb incessant accidents at the various construction sites within the tertiary institution in Rivers State.

Keywords: *Hauling process, construction, accidents, transportation, risk, equipment failure.*

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Introduction

The construction industry has long been recognized as a vital driver of economic growth

and development, playing a pivotal role in the shaping of industrial and infrastructural development, supporting job creation, and fueling various sectors of the economy of several

countries. The industry, according to Osei (2013) Saka & Adegbebo, (2022), and Pheng & Hou (2019) is said to stand tall among all other sectors because it provides the necessary infrastructures that stimulate national development. Despite these contributions, the construction industry has always been blamed for its high rate of accidents and fatalities. This issue has placed the construction industry among the industries with unreasonable rates of accidents, permanent and non-permanent disabilities, and even fatalities (Seyyed & Zahra, 2012). In the construction sector, accidents are unavoidable and have a higher risk compared to other occupations (Asanka & Ranasinghe, 2015).

Furthermore, according to Kadiri, et al. (2014) accident is an unplanned and unexpected occurrence that upsets the planned sequence of work resulting in loss of production, injury to personnel, damage to plant and equipment and eventually interrupting production flow (Kadiri, et al. 2014). In construction, management actions/inactions, unsafe acts of workers, non-human related events, and hazardous conditions within normal construction site activities, have been established as the root causes of accidents (Abdelhamid & Everett, 2000, Emuze, 2017 & Medani, et al 2024).

According to Wu, et al. (2016) accidents at work occur due to a lack of knowledge lack of supervision, lack of means to carry out work safely, errors in judgment, and carelessness in making decisions. The lack of a controlled working environment and the complexity and diversity of the sizes of organizations have impacts on safety performance in the construction industry (Muiruri & Mulinge, 2014). Furthermore, according to Wang et al (2016), human error is the main reason for up to 80% of all incidents and accidents in a complex high-risk industry such as in the construction of dams, bridges, refineries, highways, and nuclear power (Wang, et al. 2016).

The lack of coordination between the members of the professional team at the pre-construction stage has been found to be a contributing factor to accidents (Meng, et al 2021). Accident prevention mitigation on the construction sites is the responsibility of everyone involved in the

construction process, each duty holder in the process has a different and clear role. Many factors could be attributed to the frequent occurrence of accidents in construction sites. Gas leaks, fires, and explosion accidents on construction sites are due to negligence by workers. Construction workers who are exposed to electrical currents at construction sites suffer several bodily injuries such as flash burns or arc burns, electrical burns, shock, and thermal contact burns.

Conceptual, Theoretical and Empirical Clarifications

Hauling in Construction

Hauling in construction refers to the transportation of materials, equipment, and debris to and from a construction site. It involves moving heavy loads over short or long distances, both on-site and off-site, ensuring that all necessary resources are delivered to the right place at the right time (Chitkara, 2013; Hinze, 2011). Hauling is a fundamental part of the construction process, facilitating the movement of materials from suppliers and storage areas to the construction site and, in some cases, hauling away waste and debris (Gould & Joyce, 2019). The materials typically hauled in construction projects include aggregates like sand, gravel, and crushed stone; cement and concrete; steel beams and other structural elements; lumber and other building materials; heavy machinery and construction equipment; and waste and debris generated during the construction process (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017).

Efficient and effective hauling is crucial for the success of construction projects. It ensures that all materials and equipment are available when needed, minimizing delays in the construction timeline (Gould & Joyce, 2019; Chitkara, 2013). Proper hauling also contributes to the overall productivity of the construction site by providing the necessary resources to complete tasks efficiently (Hinze, 2011). Additionally, hauling plays a significant role in maintaining a safe and organized work environment, as it helps in the management of materials and reduction of congestion on the site (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017; Hwang & Ng, 2013).

Hauling Process Accident in Construction

Despite the fact that risks and hazards in construction are global, accident-hauling procedures are often negatively impacted and neglected. The risk of accidents in construction continues to be overlooked by governments, medical professionals, policy-making organizations, and decision-makers, and it does not receive the attention it deserves (Hinze, 2011; Idoro, 2011). While material transport practices differ from one construction company to the next, there are some foundational rules that they must follow. Since a smooth transportation of construction materials can make or break a project, neglecting a safe hauling process and strategies to optimise operations, enhance safety, and boost construction project's overall efficiency is inevitable. (IoSCM, 2024)

However, a growing number of fatal equipment failures and site accidents compelled global stakeholders, including the United Nations General Assembly, to examine safety management systems on construction sites (ILO, 2022). In response to increasing deaths on construction sites due to human error and unsafe practices, strategies were developed to reduce fatalities, aiming to stabilize and eventually lower their frequency globally (Islam, et al 2017 & Ahmed, et al 2018). In line with this, Nigeria declared May 11, 2011, as the start of the Nigeria Decade of Action for Construction Safety and Mitigation, targeting accident reduction and improved safety performance across the construction industry (Federal Ministry of Labour and Productivity [FMLP], 2011). The Rivers State Government claims that this decade-long initiative within the building industry is expected to save lives and improve occupational safety in construction ((Odeyinka et al., 2012).

Types of Hauling Equipment

A range of hauling machines are used in construction projects to move supplies, machinery, and debris. Hauling equipment comes in various forms, each designed for a specific purpose and operating environment (Gould & Joyce, 2019; Chitkara, 2013). The following are a few common categories of hauling equipment used in construction:

a. *Dump Trucks*: Dump trucks are the workhorses of hauling in the construction industry. They come in multiple sizes and configurations, including standard dump trucks, articulated dump trucks, and off-road dump trucks. Equipped with a hydraulic lift mechanism, dump trucks can easily unload materials at construction sites. They are ideal for transporting loose materials such as soil, gravel, sand, and crushed stone (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017; Hinze, 2011).

b. *Flatbed Trailers*: Flatbed trailers are versatile hauling vehicles designed to transport various goods and equipment. Their broad, flat platform free of sides or a roof facilitates the loading and unloading of large, heavy materials. They are commonly used for hauling precast concrete panels, steel beams, lumber, and large machinery (Hwang & Ng, 2013; Gould & Joyce, 2019).

c. *Crane Trucks*: Crane trucks are essential for construction tasks that involve heavy lifting. They serve a dual purpose by functioning both as hauling vehicles and lifting machines. These trucks are crucial for transporting and positioning materials that are too heavy or cumbersome for manual handling (Chitkara, 2013; Hinze, 2011)

d. *Transporter Trailers*: Often referred to as lowboy trailers, transporter trailers are designed to carry large, overweight loads. These trailers feature a low deck height and specialized loading ramps, which make it easier to load and unload heavy equipment such as bulldozers, excavators, and cranes (Gould & Joyce, 2019; Chitkara, 2013). Their use is common in heavy construction projects and mining operations where oversized machinery needs to be transported safely and efficiently (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017).

e. *Tipper*: Tipper trucks, also known as tipper trucks or tipper trailers, are equipped with a hydraulic mechanism that allows the cargo bed to be tilted, enabling the quick dumping of materials. These are essential for transporting loose materials like sand, aggregates, and construction debris and are frequently found in construction zones, mining areas, and quarries (Hinze, 2011; Hwang & Ng, 2013).

f. These are just a few of the many types of hauling equipment commonly used in construction projects. Depending on the specific demands of a project, contractors may also employ specialized hauling tools such as side dump trailers, belt trailers, or vacuum trucks to meet unique transportation requirements (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017; Gould & Joyce, 2019).

g. The importance of Hauling in Construction Projects cannot be overemphasized. In other words, hauling is essential to the overall effectiveness and success of building projects. It is imperative that construction teams, project managers, and contractors comprehend the significance of hauling (Chitkara, 2013; Gould & Joyce, 2019). Some of the main justifications for why hauling is crucial in construction projects that has been thrown up by various scholars include:

h. *Material and Equipment Transportation:* Hauling ensures that supplies and machinery reach the building site on schedule. This includes heavy equipment, lumber, steel, cement, aggregates, and other necessary materials. A steady flow of materials is maintained through careful and efficient hauling, which prevents construction delays (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017; Hinze, 2011).

i. *Optimal Resource Allocation:* Hauling ensures that supplies and equipment are delivered to the locations where they are most needed, aiding in efficient resource management. This reduces the likelihood of misplaced materials and prevents unnecessary accumulation on-site. Additionally, it allows for more efficient organization and use of the construction site's space (Hwang & Ng, 2013; Gould & Joyce, 2019).

j. *Timely Project Completion:* Meeting project deadlines requires efficient hauling. By ensuring the timely delivery of materials and equipment, hauling helps contractors and construction teams adhere to the project schedule. This is particularly critical for time-sensitive projects like infrastructure or commercial developments, where delays can have significant financial consequences (Chitkara, 2013; Hinze, 2011).

k. *Cost Savings:* Construction projects can reduce expenses when hauling operations are well-planned and executed. By optimizing delivery routes and load capacities, contractors can minimize transportation costs. Furthermore, effective hauling supports just-in-time material delivery, which reduces storage expenses and waste from excess inventory (Mahboub & Alkass, 2017; Hwang & Ng, 2013).

Accident Causation Theory

As the theoretical foundation of safety science, accident causation models provide a theoretical framework of accident analysis and prevention (Ge, et al 2022). Accident causation theories and models form the basis for many safety research fields and practices. Accidental injuries result from activities that are intended to run as planned but go awry, such as the release of energy or hazardous materials that exceed the human body's threshold limit (Haddon, 1980). The severity of an injury depends on the amount of energy involved and the vulnerability of the human tissue to that energy (Haddon, 1980). Accident causation theories can be categorized into several conceptual models: *person as cause*, *system as cause*, *person and system as cause*, and *system-person sequence as cause* (Reason, 1990). The accident causation models have been developed for more than 100 years since the accident proneness was proposed in 1919 (Fu et al., 2020; Greenwood and Woods, 1919). Waterson et al. (2015) divided the development of accident models into the age of technology, the age of human factors, and the age of complex socio-technical systems.

Accident causation models (or theories) are the theoretical foundation of safety science because they provide a theoretical framework of accident analysis and prevention (Ge et al., 2019a, b). Accident causation models are some simplified representations of reality (Abraha and Liyanage, 2015), providing a means of understanding safety phenomena (Leveson, 2012) and play an important role in many fields of safety research and practices such as investigation of accidents, designing a safer system and decision making on safety, and so on (Ge et al., 2022). Presently, there are many accident causation models proposed by safety

researchers. According to Fu et al. (2020), several of these models such as the domino model, the energy model, Swiss Cheese model, Risk Management Framework, SHIPP, STAMP, FRAM) have been developed for explaining the mechanisms that lead to accidents in the world in the past 100 years. The construction industry accidents have in no small measure contributed to this discuss.

Accident Proneness Theory (Greenwood & Woods, 1919)

According to the Accident Proneness Theory, certain individuals or demographic groups are more likely to experience accidents due to inherent psychological or behavioral traits (Greenwood & Woods, 1919). This theory, one of the earliest in accident causation research, was originally proposed by M. Greenwood and H.M. Woods during a study of industrial accidents in the early 20th century. They observed that a small number of workers were responsible for a disproportionately large number of accidents, suggesting that some people are naturally more accident-prone than others. Parpura (2019) describe this theory as one of the oldest and most controversial theories of accident causation is the accident proneness theory. This theory suggests that people who repeatedly have accidents are accident prone. Many experts according to Parpura (2019) agree that about 20% of the people have most of the accidents, whereas the remaining 80% have virtually no accidents.

The theory also posits that accident susceptibility can change with age youth may exhibit higher accident rates due to increased risk-taking energy, while older individuals might face challenges due to diminished physical capabilities or slower responses (Krause, 1993). This model emphasizes personal responsibility for accidents and implies that behavioral modification could be key to improving safety performance (Reason, 1990, Afuye, et al 2021). Although, antecedents are necessary for a behaviour to occur, it is not sufficient to ensure that the behaviour is maintained over time, however to ensure the re-occurrence of behaviour, significant individual consequences will be required. This implies that these

components must be fully implemented on construction sites, in order to bring out the desired safety behaviour, as they are complementary to each other (Afuye, et al 2021).

Empirical Review

Any physical alteration or modification to an emissions unit's operation, including its manufacture, erection, installation, demolition, or modification, that would affect actual emissions is referred to as construction (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], 2023). Accidents are unintentional, typically undesirable events that do not have a direct human cause. According to Sehsah, et al (2020), accidents usually have multiple root causes that include either an unsafe environment (e.g. poor work organization, site management, tools and equipment) and/or unsafe behavior (limited experience and skills, psychological and physical illnesses and poor knowledge about occupational safety) (Li, et al 2013). Unsafe environment and unsafe behavior are often referred to as immediate or primary causes. On the other hand, secondary causes, which are harder to identify, are also just as important; these include the failure of the management system to provide safe work systems and include failure to anticipate hazards, lack of training, and maintenance (Saleh & Othman, 2022, Sehsah, et al (2020).

Accidents are caused by both organizational and human factors. Workers who have received more education tend to follow safety procedures more closely and sustain fewer injuries (Abdalla, et al 2017). Conversely, workers with high levels of job uncertainty and discontent showed lower levels of motivation, lower adherence to safety protocols, and higher injury rates. The safety atmosphere, work satisfaction, and organizational support are some examples of organizational characteristics that affect employees' safe behavior and their overall impressions of management's concern for their well-being. Reducing the frequency of accidents will be facilitated by effective communication and information sharing (Gyekye et al., 2012). With effective communication practices, manufacturing companies according to Farell (2023), can better prevent worker injuries and

drastically reduce the chances of accidents and fatalities, by creating a culture of awareness and accountability. With this in place, communication brings all workers on the same page regarding workplace safety and compliance measures, while guaranteeing a clear awareness of how things should be and what needs to be done, along with a sense of accountability. Clear and frequent communication of potential risks, hazards and procedures practically ensures that employees remain on top of safety policies (Farell, 2023).

According to ILO (2024), information on the causes of accidents are very critical what needs to be done to either prevent or reduce them. In other words, where relevant and prompt information on accidents are available, it serves several purposes. It can demonstrate where something is wrong and what needs to be changed, while also providing the guide to the form of harmful factors that causes accidents (or near accidents), as well as describing the situations that result in damage and injuries. It is also believed that another purposes of accident information causes is that it helps to identify and describe the underlying circumstances that determine the presence of potential hazards and risky situations and that will result in optimum safety by their being altered or eliminated (ILO, 2024).

Lee, Ahn, Jeon and Suh (Lee, Ahn, Jeon and Suh, 2014), argue that construction stakeholders worldwide are transforming their organisational structures to implement sustainable construction practices that boost the “triple bottom line” of a building’s ecological, social, and financial performance. However, different criteria have been used while discussing the dimensions of sustainable construction practices, depending on the context and the levels of decision making. But traditionally, sustainable construction has been described from perspective of three interrelated dimensions of sustainable development, namely economic, social and environmental pillars (Loucks and Gladwell, 1999).

According to Schoormann, Behrens, Kolek, and Knackstedt (2016), these three key dimensions of economic, ecological, and social factors are

broadly and generally acknowledged by researchers over the years. They are also known as the Three Pillars of Sustainability. Litman (2019), agrees that sustainable construction includes a variety of environmental, social and economic issues. Accordingly, consideration must be given to the fact that different types of accident happen at different construction sites, as types and causes of an accident have been identified by various scholars (Williams et al., 2018, 2019; Radmin, 2017; Asanka & Ranasinghe, 2015; Socias et al., 2014; Maloney, 2012). Furthermore, certain factors have also been acknowledged as those responsible for the vehicle-related accidents, and they include visual or audible contact failure, mechanical failure, driving ability of the operator, crowding workers into one area (congestion), driving on slopes that are too steep, and speedy movement especially around bends (Williams et al., 2019).

Several researchers and practitioners in the construction industry have identified several types of accidents using construction accident investigation and reporting systems (Williams, et al 2019). However, a sufficient explanation for accident is lacking. Therefore, the theories of accident cause and human errors must be investigated. Due to the unique characteristics of the construction industry, human errors and accident causes must be understood. Winge, et al (2018) presented the Accident Root Causes Tracing Model (ARCTM), created especially for the construction sector, was used in this study.

According to ARCTM, there are three main reasons for accidents: (1) not identifying an unsafe condition that was present before or developed after an activity started; (2) carrying out work even after noticing an unsafe condition; and (3) acting unsafely despite the initial conditions. According to Medani, et al (2024), the ARCTM highlights how critical it is to comprehend unsafe conditions during work, attributing them to four primary causes: (1) mismanagement; (2) worker or colleague misconduct; (3) non-human-related incidents; and (4) an unsafe condition inherent to the original construction site. As a result, the ARCTM offers a comprehensive framework for understanding construction site accidents by acknowledging the possible contributions of

both management and labor to the accident process. Preventative action is needed for efficient accident avoidance (Winge, et al 2018, Medani, et al 2024).

According to Sehsah, et al (2020), the construction industry is characterized by a high prevalence of accidents and injuries. Inadequate risk management measures, including failure to use or incorrect use of personal protective equipment (PPE) may significantly increase the risk of accidents. Besides, they further concluded that major immediate causes were due to failure to use personal protective equipment; improper loading or placement of equipment or supplies; failure to warn co-workers or to secure equipment; and improper use of equipment.

Materials and Methods

The study employed the cross-sectional survey research design. The cross-sectional research design gives clarity of the work, detailed and

definite explanation concerning the situation and aspects under examination. The population for this study comprised male and female within the age of 18 to 60 years above that are working at the construction sites in the selected four Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. With the aid of Taro Yamane formula, simple random sampling technique was employed in selecting the sample framework. A total population 725 was used for this study, The sample size population for the study is shown in Table 1. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used for the analysis. Descriptive statistics involved the use of frequencies and percentages to express the responses from the questionnaire. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation analysis to show the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 1. Sample Size Population for the Study

S/N	Names of Institution	Population of Workers	Sample Size of Population
1	University of Port Harcourt	300	$300 \times 399 / 725 = 165$
2	Ignatius Ajuru University	140	$140 \times 399 / 725 = 77$
3	Rivers State University	215	$215 \times 399 / 725 = 118$
4	Rivers State Polytechnic	70	$70 \times 399 / 725 = 39$
	Total	725	399

Study Area

Rivers, state, southern Nigeria, comprising the Niger River delta on the Gulf of Guinea. It is bounded by the states of Anambra and Imo on the north, Abia and Akwa Ibom on the east, and Bayelsa and Delta on the west. River's state contains mangrove swamps, tropical rainforest, and many rivers. Several Ijo fishing settlements in what is now Rivers including Abonnema, Degema, Okrika, Bonny, Brass, Akassa, Nembe (Nimbi), and New Calabar became important in the early 19th century because of their trade in enslaved people and later for the export of palm oil and palm kernels. Incorporated as part of the Oil Rivers Protectorate in 1885 and Niger Coast Protectorate in 1893, the area became part of the amalgamated British colony and protectorate of Nigeria in 1914. In 1976 some parts of the

Ndoni territory in former Bendel state were added to Rivers State.

Results and Discussions

Hauling Process of Accident in Construction Within Tertiary Institution in the Study Area

Table 2. shows the analysis on the construction site accidents risks. On manual handling, 50 respondents which represent 12.9% of the sampled participants strongly disagree that manual handling caused accident at construction site, 80 respondents which represent 20.7% of the sampled participants disagree that manual handling constituted to the construction sites accident, 255 respondents which represent 66.2% of the sampled participants strongly agreed that manual handling caused accidents at

construction site in the study area. Based on the above result 66.2% indicated that majority of the sampled participants strongly agreed that manual handling caused accidents at construction sites in the study area. On electric shock, the result analysed that 39 respondents which represent 10.1% of the participants strongly disagree that electric shock was the construction sites accidents risk, 69 respondents which represent 17.9% disagree that electric shock was the construction sites accidents risk, while 277 respondents which represent 71.9% strongly agree that electric shock was the construction sites accidents risk.

It was showed that majority of the sampled participants believed that electric shock was the one of the factors that caused accident at construction sites and it also claimed that the electric shock caused high risk of accident at construction sites in the study area. On defective equipment, the result showed that 115 respondents which represent 29.9% strongly disagree that defective equipment was the construction sites accidents risk, 50 respondents which represent 12.9% also disagree that defective equipment was the construction sites accidents risk, while 220 respondents which represent 57.1% of the sampled participants strongly agree that defective equipment was the construction sites accidents risk. Based on the above result 57.1% it was depicted that defective

equipment causes accident and risk at construction sites.

On fail from height, the analysis shows that 60 respondents which represent 15.6% in the study area strongly disagree that fails from height causes the accident at construction site, 45 respondents which represent 11.6% of the sampled participant disagree that fails from height causes accident at the construction site while, 280 respondents which represent 72.7% of the sampled participants strongly agree that fails from height causes accident at the construction site. On slips, trips and fall, 75 respondents which represent 19.5% strongly disagree that slips, trips and fall were not the causes of the accident at construction sites in the study area, 28 respondents which represent 7.3% of the sampled participants disagree that slips, trips and fall were not the causes of the accident at construction sites in the study area while, 280 respondents which represent 72.7% of the sample participants strongly agree that slips, trips and fall were not the causes of the accident at construction sites in the study area. Based on the result above 72.7% indicated that majority of the sample respondents strongly agree that slips, trips and fall were the causes of the accidents at construction sites in the study area.

Table 2. Construction Sites Accidents Risks

Items	Responses	Frequency	Percent
Manual Handling	Strongly disagree	50	12.9
	Disagree	80	20.7
	Agree	115	29.9
	Strongly agree	140	36.6
	Total	385	100.0
Electric shock	Responses	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly disagree	39	10.1
	Disagree	69	17.9
	Agree	162	42.1
	Strongly agree	115	29.9
Total	385	100.0	
Defective equipment	Responses	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly disagree	115	29.9
	Disagree	50	12.9
	Agree	140	36.4
	Strongly agree	80	20.7
Total	385	100.0	

Fails from height	Responses	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly disagree	60	15.6
	Disagree	45	11.6
	Agree	123	31.9
	Strongly agree	157	40.8
	Total	385	100.0
Slips, trips and fall	Responses	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly disagree	75	19.5
	Disagree	28	7.3
	Agree	137	35.6
	Strongly agree	145	37.7
	Total	385	100.0

Hypothesis Testing

The formulated hypothesis was tested at 5% level of significance and the hypothesis was validated base on the value obtained of the P-value set at $\alpha = 0.05$. In testing the hypothesis, if the p-value is small (i.e. $p < 0.05$) then there is strong evidence against the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This section also interpreted the hypothesis formulated in this study. The study has earlier identified five null hypotheses that were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics.

Table 2 shows the result of correlation matrix obtained for there is no significant relationship between the defective equipment and lack of emergency measure in construction sites accident risks within Tertiary Institution in Rivers State. Similarly displayed in the table is the statistical test of significance (p - value), which

makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. From the result obtained in table 4.6, the correlation coefficient (rho) showed that defective equipment and lack of emergency measure have a significant relationship on construction sites accident risks within Tertiary Institution in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient of 0.391 confirms the extent and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p 0.000 < 0.05$. The coefficient represents a strong correlation between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is significant relationship between the defective equipment and lack of emergency measure in construction sites accident risks within Tertiary Institution in Rivers State.

Table 3. Defective Equipment and Lack of Emergency Measure in Construction Sites Accident Risks within Tertiary Institution in Rivers State

			Defective equipment	Lack of emergence measure
Spearman's rho	Defective equipment	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.391**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	385	385
	Lack of emergence measure	Correlation Coefficient	.391**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	385	385

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion of Findings

Hauling Process of Accident in Construction Within Tertiary Institution in the Study Area

The research revealed that 66.2% of the participants indicated that manual handling caused accidents at construction sites in the study area, the result also further revealed that majority of the sampled participants believed that electric shock was the one of the factors that caused accident at construction sites and it also claimed that the electric shock caused high risk of accident at construction sites in the study area. The result depicted that 57.1% of the sampled respondents showed that effective equipment causes accident and risk at construction sites, thus agreeing with earlier submission by Kornfeld (2020) and Project Management Institute [PMI], (2017). with 57.1% also saying that fall from height causes accident at the construction sites. Finally, majority of the sampled respondents agree that slips, trips and fall contributed to the accident at construction sites in the study area (Ogunde et al, 2017).

These findings are consistent with theories related to theory of accident causation according to Heinrich theory and that Dyreborg et al (2022) on safety intervention for prevention of accidents at work, 88% of accidents are caused by dangerous behavior. However, current theories of accident causation suggest that organizational factors, not worker error, are more likely to be at blame. Overemphasizing risky behaviors and unsafe environments as the root causes of accidents could obscure the importance of accident prevention and draw emphasis away from human mistake. (Manuele, 2014).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Identification, measurement and description of accidents together provide the basis for what is to be done and who is to do it in order to reduce the risk. If, for example, specific exposure sources can be linked to specific technologies, it will help determine what special safety measures are necessary to control the risk. This

information may also be used to influence manufacturers and suppliers associated with the technology in question. If it can be demonstrated that frequent and very serious accidents occur in connection with specific processes, the attempt may be made to adjust the nature of the equipment, machinery, operations or work procedures that are associated with these processes.

The study indicated that the manual handling, electric shock, defective equipment, falls from height, slips, trips and fall, were factors of hauling process of accident in construction in the study area. Therefore, the study concluded that accident in construction site is a critical issue facing by the construction firms caused damaged such as loss of properties, loss of lives, makes someone disable etc. Based on the result of the study, it was recommended that there is need for risk and safety experts should be contacted to assist in implementing some of the personal protective equipment policy at the various construction industries, clients, contractors and consultants of the construction sector should ensure that every construction contract takes comprehensive account of risk and safety requirements for the project. workers and statutory bodies should ensure and demand the provision of adequate health and safety measures on site.

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